

Integrating Genre-Based and Intercultural Approaches in EFL Writing Instruction: An Analysis of Gateway to English 2

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Abstract

This study investigates how genre-based and intercultural writing instruction is implemented in the ten writing lessons of Gateway 2 English 2, the textbook used at the baccalaureate level in Morocco, drawing on Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics and Kramsch's intercultural approach. The analysis focuses on the three key metafunctions of genre—field, tenor, and mode—examining how each lesson frames the subject matter (field), the relationship between writer and audience (tenor), and the communication channel (mode) to facilitate purposeful writing. Interculturality is explored through the cultural content embedded in tasks, highlighting how learners are exposed to diverse perspectives and encouraged to negotiate meaning across cultural contexts. The study employs Bingham and Witkowsky's (2022) five-phase a priori qualitative analysis, which provides a structured framework for coding and interpreting the textbook content systematically. Findings reveal that while the lessons integrate field, tenor, and mode effectively in many tasks, explicit guidance on intercultural engagement is limited, suggesting a need for more targeted scaffolding. The research emphasizes that combining a genre-based approach with intercultural objectives enhances both textual competence and cultural awareness, enabling learners to write with communicative purpose and cultural sensitivity. Implications highlight the importance of teacher mediation and reflective activities to maximize the pedagogical potential of writing lessons in EFL contexts.

Keywords: *Genre-based instruction, Field-Tenor-Mode, Interculturality, EFL writing, Textbook analysis, Qualitative coding.*

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Introduction

According to Hyland (2007), writing in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) is a multi-knowledge activity that requires mastery of several interconnected domains:

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knowledge of the content (the subject matter being communicated), knowledge of the language (vocabulary, grammar, and syntax), knowledge of the process (planning, drafting, revising, and editing), knowledge of the genre (understanding the conventions and structure of specific text types), and knowledge of the context (the social, cultural, and situational factors that influence writing). Interculturality is another level of knowledge EFL writing needs to target; this is about the consideration of not only an understanding but also an appreciation of the sense of otherness / foreignness (Kramsh, 1993). It, in other words, “entails an awareness of one’s own cultural assumptions and those of the audience, allowing for a dialogic approach to communication” (Liddicoat & Scarino, 2013).

Accordingly, effective EFL writing is not merely about linguistic competence or grammatical accuracy. It is also about both mastering the language and understanding the social and cultural contexts of texts. As Hyland (2018) emphasizes, “Effective writing is not only about linguistic competence but also about understanding the social and cultural contexts in which texts circulate.” Seen from a Systemic Functional Linguistics view, EFL writing as a cognitive, social, and intercultural activity (Hyland, 2017), should target four levels: genre, field, tenor, and mode (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014).

Genre refers to the overall purpose and structure of a text; for example, a persuasive essay aims to convince the reader, following an introduction–argument–conclusion structure. Field concerns the subject matter or topic, such as discussing the causes of school dropout in a cause-and-effect essay. Tenor relates to the social roles and relationships between participants; for instance, a formal report for a teacher requires a more academic tone than a personal letter to a friend. Mode addresses the channel and organization of a text (written, spoken, or digital) and how ideas are sequenced for clarity. By attending to these four levels, EFL learners can produce texts that are not only linguistically accurate but also contextually appropriate and meaningful for their intended audience (Hyland, 2003).

The identification of whether or not a writing course covers components beyond linguistic structures can be done in a variety of ways. One of these is through the analysis of the learning outcomes (Mager, 1975), which are statements about “what a learner is expected to know, understand and be able to do at the end of a period of learning and how that learning is to be demonstrated” (Moon, 2002). Kennedy et al. (2006) comment that the focus on learning outcomes shifts the interest from what students do to attain their diplomas to what they can do with the diplomas they have. Seen from a genre writing perspective, this shift could mean the embrace of a pedagogy oriented towards the empowerment of learners to effectively maneuver post-degree professionalism. That is to say, as Hyland (2016) argues, “writing is not simply a matter of encoding linguistic forms, but a means of negotiating identities and relationships in professional, institutional, and disciplinary contexts.”

Another form of analysis targets the assessment criteria of learners’ written work. According to Hamp-Lyons (1991), analyzing the ways in which writing is assessed can reveal the extent to which a course extends beyond the mastery of linguistic accuracy. Weigle (2002) also stresses that analyses of writing assessment can indicate whether a writing activity moves beyond surface-level correctness to include content, organization, and purpose, since these are central to successful academic and professional communication. It can also showcase whether the assessment criteria emphasize genre awareness, audience, coherence, and rhetorical effectiveness, thereby encouraging learners to see writing as a communicative and social practice (Hyland,

2003, 2016). Moreover, investigating writing assessment criteria can explain the extent to which a writing assignment fosters higher-order skills such as critical thinking, disciplinary knowledge, and professional communication (Bloxham and Boyd, 2007).

The analysis of writing lessons in the coursebook is another means of investigating which level (or levels) of knowledge is being targeted. To serve this purpose, Cunningsworth (1995) proposes four guidelines. The first explores the extent to which the textbook “corresponds to learners’ needs...in terms of language items, skills and communicative strategies” (p. 15). The second concerns whether the coursebook enables learners to acquire language relevant to their “personal, professional, academic or whatever other situations are relevant” (p. 15). This can be achieved by “incorporating realistic situations and encouraging learners to participate in activities which help develop communicative skills and strategies” (p. 16). The third relates to whether the coursebook allows learners to adopt a learning style that suits them by providing various forms of learning. The fourth guideline emphasizes the coursebook’s role as “support for learning” in a way that “mediates between the target language and the learner” (p. 17).

When applied specifically to writing lessons, Cunningsworth’s (1995) guidelines provide a useful lens for examining whether a writing lesson goes beyond a narrow focus on linguistic structures. First, analyzing how writing tasks correspond to learners’ needs helps to show whether the lessons are limited to grammar and vocabulary practice or whether they also encourage higher-order skills such as organization, coherence, and audience awareness. Second, examining the relevance of writing activities to learners’ academic and professional contexts reveals whether the coursebook introduces authentic genres and tasks that reflect real communicative demands. Third, the presence of varied writing activities indicates whether different learning styles are being supported, which in turn determines the extent to which writing is treated as a process rather than just a product. Finally, assessing how the coursebook supports learning shows whether it merely reinforces surface-level correctness or whether it mediates between learners and the broader conventions of effective written communication.

Taken together, the aforementioned approaches to writing analysis make it possible to determine the extent to which the writing component of a coursebook goes beyond linguistic accuracy to address discourse, genre, and the communicative dimensions of writing. Building on this perspective, the present study examines how far the writing lessons in *Gateway 2* respond to learners’ needs beyond grammar and structures. In fact, Moroccan Ministry of National Education Preschool and Sports set and very clearly the learning goals writing coursebooks should seek to attain in high school. These are according to the Moroccan Ministry of National Education (2007, p. 27):

Content standard 1: learners will be able to use written language for a variety of purposes and with a variety of audiences.

Content standard 2: learners will be able to use a range of writing skills and strategies in the writing process to complete a variety of writing tasks.

Content standard 3: learners will be able to recognize and apply the cultural and rhetorical aspects of different text types to write appropriately.

Content standard 4: learners will be able to demonstrate project work skills to complete a variety of tasks effectively, individually or in groups.

The learning objectives above confirm that the official guidelines recommend teaching writing in light of genre-based and intercultural approaches (Standard 1 and Standard 3). However, what is officially recommended may not necessarily be reflected in the actual content of the coursebook. To investigate this issue, the present study analyzes the writing lessons in *Gateway 2 English 2* through the lens of Halliday's genre–field–tenor–mode framework and Kramsch's concept of interculturality. More specifically, the study addresses the following two research questions:

1. How are Halliday's variables of field, tenor, and mode represented in the writing tasks of *Gateway 2*?
2. In what ways do the writing lessons in *Gateway 2* reflect elements of interculturality as conceptualized by Kramsch?

Findings of Research Question 1, when considered alongside those of Research Question 2, should together indicate the extent to which the writing lessons in the studied coursebook go beyond the purely linguistic components of writing, such as grammar and structure, to incorporate genre and interculturality components.

Materials and Methods

The current study is a priori qualitative analysis of the writing lessons in *Gateway to English 2*. This type of analysis is described by Miles et al (2014) as “a start list of researcher generated codes based upon prior research that is appropriate for qualitative studies that build on previous research.” It is a deductive form of data analysis (Creswell, 2018; Saldaña, 2021). Justifying the choice of this type of analysis is its appropriateness to allow an in-depth examination of aspects of interculturality, as conceptualized by Kramsch, and of the genre–field–tenor–mode relationships identified by Halliday. If The findings reveal the coursebook is limited to the teaching of linguistic components, it means the lessons should be revised. After all, teaching of writing should integrate genre knowledge (Hyland, 2016) and interculturality (Kramsh, 1993).

The Coursebook

The data of this qualitative analysis was drawn from *Gateway 2 English 2*, which is a Moroccan coursebook officially prescribed by the Ministry of National Education Preschool and Sports for 2nd year baccalaureate students (12th grade level). *Gateway 2 English 2* consists of 10 units, each organized around a central theme and including lessons in vocabulary, reading, grammar, listening, speaking, and writing. In addition, each closes with a project for students to work on. This coursebook was selected because it is the official textbook used nationwide in Moroccan high schools, in parallel to three other books with the same content but in different order. Therefore, the chosen book constitutes a primary resource for teaching and learning writing in this context and analysing its writing lessons is supposed to provide insight into the pedagogical orientation of writing instruction as framed by the Moroccan national curriculum.

Procedures

Data coding in this study is guided by Bingham and Witkowsky's (2022) five-phase approach to a priori qualitative analysis. The procedure began with familiarization, involving a thorough reading of all the writing lessons in *Gateway to English 2*. Next, the researcher developed codes based on Halliday's genre–field–tenor–mode framework

and Kramersch’s concept of interculturality. These frameworks were selected to capture both the linguistic-contextual dimensions of writing instruction (through Halliday’s model) and the cultural-reflective dimension (through Kramersch’s notion of interculturality).

Table 1 below presents the operational definitions of the coding categories used in the analysis:

Table 1. Coding Categories for Analyzing Writing Lessons in *Gateway to English 2*

Dimension	Theoretical Source	Sample Codes	Example Indicators in Writing Tasks
Genre	Halliday (SFL)	Narrative, Descriptive, Expository, Argumentative, Functional (e.g., letter, report)	Writing a story, describing a person, writing an opinion paragraph
Field	Halliday (SFL)	Education, Culture, Youth, Citizenship, Technology, etc.	Topic or experiential focus of the writing task
Tenor	Halliday (SFL)	Formal/Informal; Peer/Teacher/Audience relationship	Level of formality or addressee implied in the prompt
Mode	Halliday (SFL)	Written/Spoken; Monologic/Dialogic; Planned/Interactive	Mode of communication (e.g., individual essay vs. dialogue writing)
Interculturality	Kramersch (1993)	Comparison, Reflection, Empathy, Mediation	Opportunities for students to compare cultures, reflect on identity, or express intercultural understanding

This was followed by code application, whereby each writing task was examined and assigned to the relevant predefined categories. Subsequently, the researcher identified patterns by observing recurring trends across the tasks—for instance, the prevalence of certain genres or intercultural themes. Finally, the results were interpreted in light of the study’s research questions to evaluate how *Gateway to English 2* fosters genre awareness, contextualized writing, and intercultural competence.

To illustrate how these categories were applied in practice, the following example (table 2) shows the coding of one writing lesson from unit 4: “Women and Power.”

Table 2. Ranked Coding Analysis of the Writing Lesson (*Gateway to English 2*, p. 56)

Dimension	Description of Task Feature Across A–E	Code Applied	Justification / Evidence	Level
Genre	Full process: brainstorming → planning → outlining → drafting → revising an argumentative essay.	Argumentative / Process Writing	Clear, explicit steps guiding students to produce a full argumentative text.	HIGH

Field	Focus on women's political, social, and economic contributions to development.	Social Issues / Gender & Development	Strongly anchored in a meaningful societal topic with multiple subdomains.	HIGH
Tenor	Peer-to-peer interaction: group work, class sharing, partner feedback.	Collaborative / Equal-status Interaction	Consistent peer involvement, but no explicit work with varied audiences or shifts in register.	MODERATE
Mode	Oral discussion → written outlining → extended written text → written revision.	Oral–Written Hybrid / Interactive–Monologic	Balanced integration of oral and written modes, but written production is the main focus.	HIGH
Interculturality	Students reflect on women's roles in society, but no explicit intercultural comparison is required.	Reflection / Emerging Cultural Awareness	Cultural thinking is implied but not fully developed (no cross-cultural dialogue or critical intercultural tasks).	LOW–MODERATE

Results

This section presents the major findings of the analysis of the ten writing lessons in Gateway to English 2. The results are organized according to the five analytical dimensions (genre, field, tenor, mode, and interculturality) and are supported by the overall ratings illustrated in the figure below (figure 1).

Figure 1. Average Ratings of Genre and Interculture Dimensions in Gateway 2 English 2

Figure 1 presents the average ratings of the ten writing lessons in *Gateway to English 2* across the five analytical dimensions: genre, field, tenor, mode, and interculturality. It reveals a consistent pattern in which three dimensions (genre, field, and mode) are

strongly emphasized throughout the textbook, while tenor receives moderate attention and interculturality remains the least developed dimension.

The genre dimension scores the highest and this indicates how the textbook provides clear guidance on the structural features of writing tasks, particularly expository and argumentative genres. Most writing lessons follow a recognizable process-writing sequence, including brainstorming, outlining, drafting, and revising. This strong emphasis on genre suggests that the textbook prioritizes the development of organized, coherent, and purpose-driven written discourse.

Similarly, the field dimension also shows a high level of integration. In fact, the writing tasks consistently engage learners with meaningful and socially relevant topics, such as education, women's participation in development, voluntary work, technology, and citizenship. These topics draw on learners' experiential knowledge and encourage connections between classroom writing and broader societal issues, which explains the strong rating observed in the graph.

Additionally, the mode dimension likewise displays a high level of development. Writing lessons frequently combine oral interaction with written planning and extended written production. The systematic shift from spoken meaning-making (e.g., group discussions and mind maps) to written elaboration reflects a strong alignment with process-oriented pedagogy. This multimodal progression contributes to the high average mode rating.

In contrast, the tenor dimension receives only a moderate rating. Although many activities involve peer interaction, such as collaborative brainstorming or exchanging drafts, most final writing tasks are directed to a generic classroom audience. Accordingly, there is limited variation in communicative roles or audiences. Students rarely write for authentic purposes or real-world readers beyond the classroom environment, which restricts the development of audience awareness.

Finally, interculturality records the lowest rating across all dimensions. While several writing topics touch indirectly on culturally rich issues - weddings, gender roles, or education- very few tasks explicitly require learners to compare cultural perspectives, reflect on identity, or interpret cultural differences. Interculturality therefore remains largely implicit, emerging only through content rather than through task design. This may explain the consistently low average performance of this dimension in the graph.

Discussion

The analysis of the ten writing lessons in *Gateway to English 2* revealed clear patterns in how the textbook approaches writing instruction, with strong emphasis on genre, field, and mode, and comparatively weaker attention to tenor and interculturality. These findings resonate with, and in some cases diverge from, existing research on EFL writing materials. This section discusses these results in light of previous scholarly work.

Overall, the consistently high rating for the genre dimension reflects the textbook's strong orientation toward expository and argumentative writing. This observation supports Hyland's (2007) view that many EFL materials prioritize "school-based genres" such as essays because they are aligned with examination demands and academic expectations. Similar conclusions were drawn by Emilia (2011), who found that genre-based writing tasks in EFL textbooks tend to privilege essays and expository

writing over narrative or personal expression. The instructional sequences in *Gateway to English 2*, which frequently include brainstorming, outlining, drafting, and revising, mirror the structured genre pedagogy described in these studies. The findings therefore confirm what Hyland and Emilia observe: EFL textbooks often provide a strong foundation in formal, academic writing genres while offering limited space for creative or alternative text types.

The field dimension also scored high across all lessons, indicating a strong alignment between writing tasks and socially meaningful topics. This parallels Carter and Nunan's (2001) argument that communicative textbooks increasingly use "socially grounded content" to make language learning relevant to learners' real-world experiences. The writing tasks analyzed in this study address themes such as education, youth, women's participation in development, citizenship, and environmental issues - all fields that invite students to draw on local knowledge and personal experience. However, similar to findings in previous research, the field content, while broad and meaningful, does not always push learners toward critical engagement. Many tasks ask students to describe or explain rather than interrogate or evaluate underlying social assumptions, echoing the observation by Benesch (1999) that EFL materials often remain "safe" by presenting socially relevant topics without encouraging deeper critique.

In contrast, the tenor dimension received a moderate rating, reflecting limited variation in audience or communicative roles. This finding aligns with Gebhard's (2016) and Lee's (2018) critiques that writing tasks in pedagogical materials tend to default to a "student-to-teacher" tenor or peer interaction, without exposing learners to authentic or diverse audiences. The writing lessons in *Gateway to English 2* commonly ask students to write paragraphs, essays, or emails without specifying a real-world recipient or communicative situation. As Lee (2018) notes, such decontextualized writing tasks "constrain learner awareness of how audience shapes language choices." The results of this study confirm this pattern: although peer collaboration is encouraged in the stages of brainstorming and revising, the communicative purpose of the final text remains vague or purely academic.

The mode dimension, which also scored high, indicates that the textbook makes consistent use of process-writing principles. This matches Badger and White's (2000) finding that many modern EFL textbooks incorporate elements of process writing, such as drafting, revising, and peer feedback. However, Badger and White also note that the implementation of process writing varies widely, with some materials emphasizing controlled practice more heavily than extended writing. *Gateway to English 2* appears relatively balanced: many lessons begin with oral or collaborative activities before moving to structured written tasks, demonstrating a holistic integration of oral and written modes. This supports Richards' (2015) observation that effective EFL materials increasingly blend spoken interaction with written composition to scaffold learners' meaning-making.

Finally, the low rating for the interculturality dimension echoes a well-established pattern in the literature. A number of scholars, including Byram (1997), Sercu (2005), and Yuen (2011), have documented that intercultural competence tends to be the least developed component in EFL textbooks. Yuen (2011) notes that cultural elements in many textbooks are presented as "surface-level information," lacking opportunities for students to compare cultural values, examine multiple perspectives, or reflect critically on identity. The findings from this study reinforce these concerns. While the writing tasks occasionally touch on culturally embedded topics such as weddings or gender roles, they rarely require learners to engage in intercultural comparison or mediation.

As Kramersch (1993) argues, genuine interculturality involves understanding the symbolic systems that shape cultural meaning; however, the tasks in Gateway to English 2 do not explicitly prompt such reflection.

Conclusion

This study evaluated the writing lessons in Gateway to English 2 using Halliday's genre–field–tenor–mode framework and Kramersch's concept of interculturality. The findings show that the textbook aligns with international trends in EFL material design: strong in genre structure, relevant in field content, and process-oriented in mode, while offering only moderate support for tenor and minimal development of interculturality. Taken together, the results highlight the need for writing materials that include more authentic audiences, more varied communicative roles, and more explicit intercultural tasks that foster comparison, empathy, and critical cultural awareness. These enhancements would address some of the limitations identified in this study and align the textbook more closely with contemporary goals for intercultural communicative competence. Future research may extend this analysis to classroom implementation, teacher mediation, or comparisons across different Moroccan EFL textbooks to determine whether similar patterns hold across the national teaching context.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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